

TELEVISION LANGUAGE AS A LANGUAGE FEATURES OF ELECTRONIC MASS MEDIA

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Television emerges as an audiovisual medium of mass communication that combines the sound we hear and the image we see. According to TV language researcher O.V. Aleksandrova, telecommunication is, first of all, mass communication. It is an exchange of information in which millions of people from different groups and strata receive and use information. Television discourse is a complex system that combines different parameters, the specifics of the language, the specificity of styles and themes, the diversity of genres. Today, the language of audiovisual means attracts the attention of many linguists.

In the process of studying the specifics of audiovisual media, television theorists focused on the possibilities of television and the characteristics of the genres of television journalism. They approached the problems of teletext from the point of view of traditional practical stylistics, lexical and syntactic stylistics of teletext.

S.V.Svetana studied telegraph speech in her monograph "Television Speech: Functions and Structure" and introduced the concept of "television speech" as a scientific term. After analyzing television texts, the author conducted an experiment to determine the characteristics of television speech and came to the following conclusions: The show has seemed a bit unfocused in recent episodes, but it's finally here.

S.V.Svetana distinguishes two types of TV shows - ready and ready. "Television performances are based on the laws of speech, so any criteria for oral presentation is the basis for television appearances," he wrote.

It is not necessary to choose the language in the teleconference, it is better to refer to the oral-literary norm. We recognize this process as a fundamental, defining expression of modern television. Today, the development of modern forms of electronic communication, the proliferation of "talking genre" television and radio programs confirm the opinion of the researcher. In the function of modern literary language, the field of mass oral communication with its main communicative spheres is growing.

Thanks to the expansion of live broadcasts, the teleconference has created a style of conversation with its literary-colloquial dictionary and syntactic structures, dialogue units, question-and-answer forms. "The moment of improvisation became necessary, the effect of the word was emphasized, the intonation was enhanced by figurative gestures and facial expressions.

Television language researcher according to S.V.Svetana, television historians and theorists felt the magical power of the image in the early stages of creating the television genre. Later, the audio-visual nature of television was discussed, but no emphasis was placed on the concept of 'sound'. Clearly, television channels transmit not only sound, noisy images, music, but also live human voice - speech. It is therefore advisable to consider the "image-sound-speech" trinity when studying television. Considering television in such a trinity, on the one hand, allows us to consider the most important features of television as one of the modern

media, and on the other hand, proves that television provides rich material for observing live speech processes.

As we can see, the image-voice-speech trio is also a complex system, each element of which is aimed at ensuring the most effective communication between the journalist and the audience. Our task is to analyze the role of speech in this trio and to show which style is most important for successful communication. In this case, we study the prozodic features of the speech of TV presenters in terms of the specific functions of television speech, the format of the TV channel, the genre of the program, the audiovisuality.

We can see the influence of extralinguistic factors on the structure of television speech. Extralinguistic factors also determine the non-linguistic constitution that creates the conditions for the realization of telepathy.

In this case, extralinguistic features are formed on the basis of a number of conditions studied by neighboring, closely related disciplines, such as logic and psychology. When we study the process of real speech communication, we consider not only the process of speech formation that psychologists focus on, but also the characteristics of the speaker (listener) and the writer (reader) who are the carrier and receiver. Information in each specific speech act.

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